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Determining species- and tissue-sensitive biogenic carbon content in wood for LCA

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Abstract. Biogenic carbon content refers to the amount of carbon dioxide absorbed during biomass growth, stored in subsequent wood products and released during incineration at its End-of-Life. This temporary storage of carbon in wood products can play an important role in climate change mitigation strategies. Life cycle assessment (LCA) is commonly used to evaluate the environmental impacts, in this case specifically the Global Warming Potential (GWP), of wood products. However, one challenge is the lack of detailed data on biogenic carbon content which varies by tree species and wood tissue. To calculate the carbon content, existing models often use simplified assumptions for carbon fraction and wood density, which can reduce accuracy. The European Horizon project Woodstock aims to develop a user-friendly LCA approach that can model biogenic carbon flows in wood products, including those made from underutilized wood types such as Hardwood and Low-Quality Wood, through accurate species- and tissue-specific carbon content data. This study thus utilizes available datasets on carbon fraction and wood density to calculate improved carbon content values based on the EN16449 standard. Comparing the carbon fraction, density and subsequent carbon content values within relevant Hardwood and Softwood species and their respective Stem, Branches and Bark tissue, showcases the significant extend of variances within the analysed wood types. A sensitivity analysis furthermore highlights the influence of the available carbon fraction and density data on the carbon content. Finally, the results suggest that underutilized wood resources like Hardwood and Low-Quality Wood can have higher carbon contents than the commonly used Softwood Stem typically employed in construction. This suggests a possible environmental incentive to increase the use of previously underutilized wood resources in construction.

1. Introduction

The European Horizon project Woodstock aims to advance climate-smart wooden construction practices in alignment with the New European Bauhaus initiative (European Commission, 2024). The central focus of the project is to promote the use of underutilized wood streams. To support this goal, Woodstock seeks to develop a user-friendly Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach capable of evaluating future wooden construction solutions. The to-be-developed approach will mainly focus on the Global Warming Potential (GWP) Impact Category by accounting for the temporal dynamics of carbon storage, such as biogenic carbon, in wooden materials. To achieve

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this objective a nuanced understanding of wood carbon content is essential to accurately reflect the diversity of wooden materials, particularly those not typically employed in conventional construction.

Current carbon accounting systems and LCA tools, however, generally employ a uniform carbon fraction value for all bio-based building materials, commonly set at 0,5 (50%) as listed in EN 16449 (CEN/TC 175, 2014), or rely on generalized conversion factors recommended by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (Aalde et al., 2006). For example, the WWF Biogenic Carbon Calculator adopts a fixed carbon fraction of 50% (WWF, 2020), while the ecoinvent database embedded in SimaPro applies a value of 49,4% for wood products (ecoinvent, 2025). A growing body of research demonstrates that applying these uniform carbon fraction values can introduce significant inaccuracies in estimating carbon contents of wooden biomass and have been shown to produce average errors of approximately 4,8% in current forest carbon estimates (Martin et al., 2018). Consequently, there is increasing emphasis on the use of region-, species-, and tissue-sensitive carbon fraction values to reduce uncertainty and improve the precision of carbon accounting (Bārdule, et al., 2021). Similarly, commonly used datasets for LCA either offer species-sensitive heartwood density values (p_w) (e.g. EN 350 (CEN/TC 38, 2016)) or general Hardwood and Softwood differentiations (e.g. ecoinvent database embedded in SimaPro (ecoinvent, 2025)), neglecting possible differences within the different tree tissues, again leading to inaccuracies when calculating the carbon content. This dichotomy between theory and practice underscores the necessity of integrating species- and tissue-sensitive carbon fraction and density data for bio-based building materials in LCA methodologies in order to calculate accurate carbon contents.

Particularly when trying to analyse differences between various wooden building materials, as aimed for within Woodstock, accurate biogenic carbon content estimates are key. This research therefore aims to consider differences in the following wood types when calculating carbon contents through density and carbon fraction values, acting as a vital step in the development of a Woodstock LCA approach and eventually improving decision making based on LCA results for wooden building materials.

- a) **Tree Species:** Different tree species might contain distinct carbon fractions and density values, thus exhibiting different carbon contents. This variability is critical to the Woodstock project, as stakeholders aim to promote the use of non-traditional species within the construction industry.

One such resource is *Hardwood*. To date, seven underutilized hardwood species with promising potential for increased utilization have been identified within the Woodstock project: *European Oak*, *Sessile Oak*, *European Beech*, *European Aspen*, *Downy Birch*, *Silver Birch*, and *Black Alder*. These species will serve as the basis for species-sensitive carbon fraction and density values. To enable a comprehensive comparison not only among hardwoods but also with the more commonly used softwoods in the timber industry, a selection of the most prevalent softwoods will also be included in the analysis (European Organisation of the Sawmill Industry, 2024). Thus, the most common softwood species from each genus have been selected: *Norway Spruce*, *Scots Pine*, *European Silver Fir*, and *European Larch*.

- b) **Wood Tissue:** Carbon fractions and density values might vary within a tree species depending on the tissue type (e.g., stem, bark, branches, etc.), thus exhibiting different

carbon contents. Recognizing these differences is especially important when assessing the identified underutilized wood resource *Low-Quality Wood*, which often includes tissue types excluded from standard construction practices.

To date the Woodstock project has identified three specific types of underutilized wood tissues: *Branches*, *Bark*, and *Stump* (stump has been excluded from this research due to limited data availability later on). To provide a comprehensive comparison, not only among underutilized wood tissues but also with more widely used tissue types in the timber industry, *Stem* wood will be analysed as an additional tissue type. Although an above-ground component, foliage was excluded from further analysis due to its limited applicability in construction. Below-ground tissue types such as coarse roots and fine roots were excluded for similar reasons.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Steps

This paper examines species- and tissue-sensitive carbon fraction, density and subsequent carbon content values for underutilized wood resources identified within the Woodstock project. Seven hardwood species (European Oak, Sessile Oak, European Beech, European Aspen, Downy Birch, Silver Birch, and Black Alder) and four softwood species (Norway Spruce, Scots Pine, European Silver Fir, and European Larch) and their respective Stem, Branches, and Bark tissue have been selected for this purpose. In the next section the data acquisition and handling methodology as well as the calculation method have been outlined. The results are then compiled into Carbon Fraction, Density, and Carbon Content segments, followed by a sensitivity analysis and a discussion and conclusion, highlighting overarching themes and trends as well as potential impact and further research areas.

2.2 Data Acquisition

To acquire robust species- and tissue-sensitive datasets, the TRY Plant Trait Database was utilized. The search resulted in one "Wood carbon database" (Martin et al., 2018), which has since been incorporated into an updated dataset titled "GLOWCAD" (Doraisami, et al., 2022) and one "Global Wood Density Database" (Zanne, 2009). Outside of TRY, one additional "Cirad wood density database" (Vieilledent G., 2018) was found. While the "GLOWCAD" dataset offers species- and tissue-sensitive carbon fraction data, neither of the two density datasets offers tissue-sensitive data entries. As no tissue-sensitive dataset for density was found, various academic papers were analysed to fill in the gap. Here, the most extensive data on species- and tissue-sensitive density values in European tree species seem to stem from Petráš et al., (2010, 2019, 2020) who conducted multiple studies on species- and tissue-sensitive basic density in Slovakia. Thus, moving forward the "GLOWCAD" dataset will be utilized for carbon fraction values while the work of Petráš et al., (2010, 2019, 2020) will be utilized to derive the density values.

2.3 Data Handling

Petráš et al., (2010, 2019, 2020) looks at the species- and tissue-sensitive basic densities of various tree species, common in Slovakia. The 2010 paper looks at the species- and tissue-sensitive density of European Aspen clones (Robusta and I-214). As I-214 (also called *Populus × euramericana*) is much more common in Europe, data for Aspen was extracted from I-214. The 2010 paper differentiates the density for each species into "the wood on tree foot (W1) and at middle of stem (W2)", "the bark on tree foot (B1) and at middle of stem (B2)", "the wood (W3) and

the bark (B3)”, “the whole small-wood of wood with bark (WB4 and WB5)”. The 2019 paper looks at the species- and tissue-sensitive density of common European softwoods, namely Spruce, Pine, Fir, and Larch (the paper only differentiates by genus, not by species). The 2019 paper differentiates the density for each species into “wood”, “bark” and “small-wood”, for three locations (“1 – on the stem foot, 2 – at the middle of the stem, 3 – at the middle of the crown”) respectively. The 2020 paper looks at the species- and tissue-sensitive density of common European hardwood species. The 2020 paper only depicts the results graphically, thus the exact density values had to be approximated to the closest 5 kg/m³. The 2020 paper differentiates the density for each species into “wood”, “bark” and “small-wood” respectively.

For easier handling of the data within this research, the original differentiations have been renamed into Stem, Branches and Bark. In cases where the original paper differentiated the tree tissue into height related categories, averages have been calculated to reflect the overall values. In instances where no data entries were available for species- and tissue-sensitive data, available data from the closest relative within the same genus was chosen (e.g. *Quercus petraea* for *Quercus robur*). Utilizing the papers with the stated parameters and limitations, data for all relevant tree species for Stem, Branches and Bark were found.

The “GLOWCAD” dataset presents species- and tissue-sensitive data entries for the non-volatile carbon fraction of dried (0% moisture content) wood. In most cases the wood has been oven-dried, while some entries indicate that the wood has been freeze-dried. The oven-drying methods can lead to different carbon fractions due to the volatile carbon contents and potentially underestimate the carbon content of other drying methods by up to 2,5% (Martin et al., 2018). While the importance of accounting for the different methods has been acknowledged, no detailed research with robust data outcomes has been conducted in this field. Thus, data entries for oven- and freeze-dried carbon fractions have been combined, and no corrections or further differentiations have been made.

Furthermore the “GLOWCAD” dataset is not only species- and tissue-sensitive but also differentiates into “dead” and “alive” wood. “Dead” wood typically refers to wood that is already decaying, whereas “alive” wood is cut from a living tree. As construction timber typically uses “alive” wood, only data entries for “alive” were considered. In instances where multiple data entries for the same species and tissue were available, a mean average was calculated. Due to insufficient data on intraspecies differences based on biome, all available data entries were included in this average regardless of biome and region. In instances where no data entries were available for tissue- and species-sensitive data, available data from the closest relative within the same genus was chosen (e.g. *Larix olgensis* for *Larix decidua*). Utilizing the dataset with the stated parameters and limitations, data for all relevant tree species and tissue types (except values for Branches of Black Alder) were found.

2.4 Calculation Method

Based on the data acquisition and handling methods outlined above, the biogenic carbon contents for 1m³, for the species (European Oak, Sessile Oak, European Beech, European Aspen, Downy Birch, Silver Birch, Black Alder, Norway Spruce, Scots Pine, European Silver Fir, and European Larch) and respective tissue types (Stem, Branches, and Bark) were calculated according to EN16449 (CEN/TC 175, 2014). As defined in EN 16449 the general formula to calculate the amount of biogenic carbon content in wood is as shown in Eq. (1):

$$P_{CO_2} = \frac{44}{12} * cf * \frac{\rho_w * V_w}{1 + \frac{\omega}{100}} \quad (1)$$

where

P_{CO_2} is the biogenic carbon oxidized as carbon dioxide emissions from the product system into the atmosphere (e.g. energy use at the end-of-life) (kg);

cf is the carbon fraction of woody biomass (oven dry mass), 0,5 as the default value;

ω is the moisture content of the product (e.g. 12 (%));

p_{ω} is the density of woody biomass at the product at that moisture content (kg/ m³);

V_{ω} is the volume of the solid wood product at that moisture content (m³).

To accurately calculate and compare the biogenic carbon content (P_{CO_2}) of different tree species and tissues, the volume (V_{ω}) is set at 1 m³. Furthermore, the moisture content (ω) is set at 12%, a commonly used assumption for construction timber (CEN/TC 175, 2014). Thus, only the carbon fraction (cf) and density (p_{ω}) values require additional, species- and tissue-sensitive data. While the carbon fraction (cf) data from the “GLOWCAD” dataset can be directly used in the above formula, the density values found in the studies of Petráš et al. are listed for the basic density (p_{basic}) and not the moisture specific density at 12% ($p_{\omega 12\%}$). To reflect the physical properties of construction timber, the basic density (p_{basic}), was converted to the density at 12% moisture content ($p_{\omega 12\%}$). This conversion was achieved by inverting the commonly used empirical relationship between (p_{basic}), and ($p_{\omega 12\%}$), resulting in Eq. (2) (Vieilledent G., 2018).

$$(p_{basic}), = 0,828 * (p_{\omega 12\%}), \quad (2)$$

Rearranging the equation yields Eq. (3):

$$(p_{\omega 12\%}) = \frac{(p_{basic})}{0,828} = 1,21 * (p_{basic}). \quad (3)$$

The converted moisture specific density values at 12% ($p_{\omega 12\%}$) can then be used for the density (p_{ω}) in the biogenic carbon content formula Eq. (1).

3. Results

This section depicts the differences between *Hardwood* and *Softwood* averages, for the tissue types of *Stem*, *Branches*, and *Bark* in regard to the carbon fraction and density values compiled from the “GLOWCAD” dataset and the research conducted by Petráš et al., as well as the calculated carbon contents based on EN16449 (Figure 1). Figure 1 presents results grouped by wood type. The Softwood category is based on four data points, while the Hardwood category includes six data points for Carbon Fraction and Carbon Content respectively, and seven data points for Density. Each subsection lists the maximum, minimum, and mean average values including the standard and maximum deviation in %. Furthermore, for each subsection a comparison of the different tissue types within, as well as between the Softwood and Hardwood categories is given. Individual values for all species and tissue types are not listed here. As this research is part of an ongoing project, the research data will be added to the Zenodo data depository (WoodStock Community) later. In the meantime, it can be requested directly from the authors.

Figure 1. Box and Whisker Plot of Carbon Fraction, Density, and Carbon Content values for Stem, Branches, and Bark grouped by wood type: Softwood (bright green) and Hardwood (dark green).

3.1 Non-volatile Carbon Fraction of fully dried Wood

Within the group of analysed wood types, the average non-volatile carbon fraction of fully dried wood ranges from 45,5% in the Stem of European Aspen to 55,7% in the Bark of Downy Birch. Averaging $48,97\% \pm 2,88\%$, the carbon fraction values represent a standard deviation of 6% and deviations of up to 14% (Downy Birch, Bark). On average Bark exhibits the highest carbon fraction (50,04%), followed by Branches (49,22%) and Stem (47,67%). Thus, Bark exhibits higher relative carbon fraction values than Stem (+5%) and Branches (+2%).

Softwood contains the highest carbon fraction in Bark (50,19%), followed by Branches (49,97%) and Stem (48,06%), while Hardwood, exhibits the highest carbon fraction in Bark (49,95%) followed by Branches (48,72%) and Stem (47,45%) Thus, Softwood exhibits higher relative carbon fraction values than Hardwood in Stem (+1%), Branches (+3%), and Bark (+0%).

3.2 Density of wood types at 12% moisture content

Within the group of analysed wood types, the average density at 12% moisture content ranges from $402,93 \text{ kg/m}^3$ in the Bark of Scots Pine to $786,5 \text{ kg/m}^3$ in the Bark of the European Beech. Averaging $607,71 \pm 105,75 \text{ kg/m}^3$, the density values represent a standard deviation of 17% and deviations of up to 34% (Scots Pine, Bark). On average Branches exhibits the highest

density (624,76 kg/m³), followed by Bark (614,97 kg/m³) and Stem (583,41 kg/m³). Thus, Branches exhibits higher relative density values than Stem (+7%) and Bark (+2%).

Softwood contains the highest density in Branches (601,07 kg/m³), followed by Bark (517,28 kg/m³) and Stem (500,94 kg/m³), while Hardwood, exhibits the highest density in Bark (670,79 kg/m³) followed by Branches (638,30 kg/m³) and Stem (630,53 kg/m³). Thus, Hardwood exhibits higher relative density values than Softwood in Stem (+26%), Branches (+6%), and Bark (+30%).

3.3 Biogenic Carbon Content for 1m³

Within the group of analysed wood types, the average biogenic carbon content for 1m³ ranges from 675,78 kgCO₂ in the Bark of Scots Pine to 1345,94 kgCO₂ in the Bark of the Silver Birch and Downy Birch. Averaging 975,67 ± 186,67kgCO₂, the carbon content values represent a standard deviation of 19% and deviations of up to 38% (Silver Birch and Downy Birch, Bark). On average Bark exhibits the highest carbon content (1007,41kgCO₂), followed by Branches (1006,78 kgCO₂), and Stem (910,44 kgCO₂). Thus, Bark exhibits higher relative carbon content values than Stem (+11%) and Branches (+0%).

Softwood contains the highest carbon content in Branches (983,35 kgCO₂), followed by Bark (849,99 kgCO₂) and Stem (788,13 kgCO₂), while Hardwood, exhibits the highest carbon content in Bark (1096,92 kgCO₂) followed by Branches (1018,16 kgCO₂) and Stem (979,39 kgCO₂). Thus, Hardwood exhibits higher relative carbon content values than Softwood in Stem (+24%), Branches (+4%), and Bark (+29%).

4. Sensitivity Analysis

Due to the limitations and uncertainties described in the methodology, a sensitivity analysis regarding the carbon content results was conducted. Two distinct scenarios were analysed and compared to the baseline scenario (see section 3.3). To understand the impact of utilizing species- and tissue-sensitive carbon fractions, instead of the contemporary assumption of a 50% flat carbon fraction value for all wood types, scenario (1) assumes a 50% carbon fraction for all species and respective tissue types. Scenario (2) on the other hand only utilizes the species-sensitive heartwood density values listed in EN350, instead of the species- and tissue-sensitive density values according to the research conducted by Petráš et al, in order to analyse deviations in the carbon content based on different density assumptions.

4.1 Scenario 1: 50% flat Carbon Fraction

In this scenario the biogenic carbon content is calculated in the same way as in the baseline scenario. However, the species- and tissue-sensitive carbon fraction values derived from the "GLOWCAD" dataset were replaced by a 50% carbon fraction assumption for all species and respective tissue types.

Within the group of analysed wood types, the average biogenic carbon content for 1m³ now ranges from 659,56 kgCO₂ in the Bark of Scots Pine to 1287,43 kgCO₂ in the Bark of the European Beech. Averaging 994,77 ± 175,81 kgCO₂, the carbon content values represent a standard deviation of 17% and deviations of up to 34% (Scots Pine, Bark). On average Branches exhibits the highest carbon content (1022,68 kgCO₂), followed by Bark (1006,64 kgCO₂), and Stem (994,77 kgCO₂). Thus, Branches exhibits higher carbon content values than Stem (+7%), and Bark (+2%).

Softwood contains the highest carbon content in Branches (983,89 kgCO₂), followed by Bark (846,73 kgCO₂) and Stem (819,99 kgCO₂), while Hardwood, exhibits the highest carbon content in Bark (1098,02 kgCO₂) followed by Branches (1044,84 kgCO₂) and Stem (1032,12

kgCO₂) Thus, Hardwood exhibits higher carbon content values than Softwood in Stem (+26%), Branches (+6%), and Bark (+30%).

Compared to the Baseline, Scenario 1 exhibits a 2% higher carbon content on average, with a standard deviation from the baseline of 6% and deviations of up to 10% (Downy Birch and Silver Birch, Bark). In Table 1 the relative deviations of the average carbon content per tissue type from the Baseline in % are listed.

Table 1. Change in carbon content in Scenario 1 relative to the Baseline (% change, relative).

Tissue Type	Total	Softwood	Hardwood
Stem	+5%	+4%	+5%
Branches	+2%	+0%	+3%
Bark	-0%	-0%	+0%

4.2 Scenario 2: Species-sensitive Density

In this scenario the biogenic carbon content is calculated in the same way as in the baseline scenario. However, the species- and tissue-sensitive density values derived from the research conducted by Petras et al. were replaced by species-sensitive heartwood density values according to EN350 for all species and respective tissue types. EN 350 lists three different density values for each species, for this scenario the median values were selected.

Within the group of analysed wood types, the average biogenic carbon content for 1m³ now ranges from 655,42 kgCO₂ in the Stem of European Aspen to 1203,52 kgCO₂ in the Bark of the Downy Birch and Silver Birch. Averaging 945,69 ± 165,24 kgCO₂, the carbon content values represent a standard deviation of 17% and deviations of up to 31% (European Aspen, Stem). On average Bark exhibits the highest carbon content (963,86 kgCO₂), followed by branches (956,58 kgCO₂), and Stem (917,63 kgCO₂). Thus, Bark exhibits higher carbon content values than Stem (+5%), and Branches (+1%).

Softwood contains the highest carbon content in Bark (854,82 kgCO₂), followed by Branches (853,54 kgCO₂) and Stem (820,53 kgCO₂), while Hardwood exhibits the highest carbon content in Bark (1026,17 kgCO₂), followed by Branches (1025,27 kgCO₂) and Stem (973,11 kgCO₂) Thus, Hardwood exhibits higher carbon content values than Softwood in Stem (+19%), Branches (+20%), and Bark (+20%).

Compared to the Baseline, Scenario 2 exhibits a 3% lower carbon content on average, with a standard deviation from the baseline of 12% and deviations of up to 29% (Scots Pine, Bark). In Table 2 the relative deviation of the average carbon content per tissue type from the Baseline in % are listed.

Table 2. Change in carbon content in Scenario 2 relative to the Baseline (% change, relative).

Tissue Type	Total	Softwood	Hardwood
Stem	+2%	+5%	+1%
Branches	-5%	-13%	0%
Bark	-6%	-1%	-8%

5. Conclusion

The non-volatile carbon fractions of fully dried wood types averaged 48,97%, where Softwood averaged 49,52% and Hardwood averaged 48,71% across all tissue types. These findings are consistent with previous research, e.g. (Martin et al., 2018), which showed that, on average Softwood exhibits higher carbon fractions than Hardwood in Stem, Branches and Bark respectively. Among these tissues, Bark had the highest average carbon fraction, in both Softwood and Hardwood, followed by Branches and then Stem. These trends, however, should not lead to generalizations as carbon fractions are highly species- and tissue-sensitive, e.g. the Bark of the hardwood Downy Birch exhibits the highest observed carbon fraction overall (55,7%). Furthermore, these findings reaffirm, that assuming an average 50% carbon fraction can lead to an overestimation in the biogenic carbon content storage capacity of wood. Within the group of analysed tissue types only Bark exhibited a 50,04% carbon fraction while Branches (49,22%) and Stem (47,67%) exhibited lower carbon fractions than 50%. The sensitivity analysis scenario 1 highlighted the effect of using a flat 50% carbon fraction assumption which consequently led to an average overestimation of carbon content of 2% with deviations of up to 10% from the baseline for cases that exhibit either a significantly higher or lower carbon fraction than 50%.

The density of wood types at 12% moisture content averaged 607,71 kg/m³, where Softwood averaged a lower density of 547,80 kg/m³ than Hardwood (649,22 kg/m³) across all tissue types. These findings are in line with contemporary knowledge of average Softwood and Hardwood densities and these differences are subsequently represented in LCA databases such as (ecoinvent, 2025). This research, however, has shown that there are significant density variances within Softwood and Hardwood categories as well as within a species based on tissue types. Here Branches showcased the highest average density in Softwood, while Bark exhibited the highest average density in Hardwood, highlighting the need for species- and tissue-sensitive density data. The sensitivity analysis scenario 2 showcased the effect of using alternative species-sensitive heartwood density values for the calculation of carbon contents. Compared to the baseline, Stem showed a 2% higher carbon content on average, which might be due to a multitude of factors, one of which could be that the density values of EN350 are for heartwood, while the research conducted by Petráš et al. focused on the whole Stem. Branches and Bark on the other hand exhibit a 5% and 6% lower carbon content respectively, which is likely due to use of heartwood density values for Branches and Bark, which are generally lower than the tissue-sensitive density values for Branches and Bark collected by Petráš et al.

The biogenic carbon content for 1m³ averaged 975,67 kgCO₂, where Softwood averaged a lower carbon content of 887,27 kgCO₂ than Hardwood (1037,51 kgCO₂) across all tissue types. This research has shown that on average Hardwood exhibit a higher mean and median carbon content than Softwood in their Stem, Branches and Bark respectively, highlighting significant variances within Softwood and Hardwood categories. Though Branches and Bark exhibit similar carbon content values across Softwood and Hardwood averages, Softwood showed the highest average carbon content in Branches while Hardwood exhibited the highest average content in Bark, highlighting the need for species- and tissue-sensitive carbon content data.

5.1 Outlook

For Woodstock these findings reaffirm the assumption that underutilized wood resources such as Hardwood, and Low-Quality Wood such as Bark and Branches can be incentivized through LCAs, as they can sequester more biogenic carbon than the commonly used Stem of Softwood in the construction industry. While the carbon content in itself can already be included as additional

information in EPDs, the carbon content can also influence the result of GWP significantly depending on the LCA approach used. As dynamic LCAs (dLCA), which account for the timing of emissions, are gaining increasing attention within the EU, accurate carbon content data becomes vital to perform robust LCAs (European Commission, 2024). Thus, next steps of this research will analyse the effect of the calculated carbon contents on GWP across different dLCA methods and see how different variables and assumptions such as rotation period and storage period influence the results.

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